

The Flashback Project: rescuing disk-based content from the 1980s to the current day.

Maureen Pennock
The British Library

Peter May
The British Library

Michael Day
The British Library

Kevin Davies
The British Library

Simon Whibley
The British Library

Akiko Kimura
The British Library

Edith Halvarsson
The British Library

Abstract

This paper introduces the British Library's Flashback project, a proof-of-concept that explored the practical challenges of preserving digital content stored on physical media (magnetic and optical disks) using a sample of content from hybrid collection items dating from between 1980 and 2010. It describes some of the activities undertaken by the project, including: the initial collection profiling and sampling of content, the extraction of content from the disks, and the project team's experiments with identifying and applying preservation approaches to the content, which included both emulation and migration. It concludes with some general observations on the approaches taken and looks forward to the second phase of the project.

Introduction

The British Library is the UK's national deposit centre for published content. Its collections are vast and comprise everything from books and journals, to maps, newspapers, electoral registers, and patent specifications, in both hard-copy and electronic form. It also contains one of the largest collections of recorded sound in the world. The Library's digital preservation team has been working on strategies to preserve the digital elements of the collections since around 2005. Recently, attention has turned to digital content acquired before this date, content that is typically still stored on its acquisition media, with examples in the Library's collections dating back to the 1980s. This 'legacy' content is an excellent corpus for testing preservation

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Correspondence should be addressed to Maureen Pennock, The British Library, Boston Spa, Wetherby, North Yorkshire, LS 23 7BQ. Email: maureen.pennock@bl.uk

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strategies as it is reliant on technology which is already, in many cases, institutionally obsolete.¹

Institutional obsolescence is not the only issue and a second complication is the lifespan of the storage media used, which are typically floppy disks or Compact Discs (CDs). It is notoriously difficult to calculate disc lifespans with any certainty due to huge variations in original disc quality and storage/usage conditions but, to put this in some temporal context, the Optical Storage Technology Association (2003) estimates the unrecorded shelf life of a CD-R (Compact Disc-Recordable) or CD-RW (Compact Discs-Rewriteable) disc at between five and ten years. Accurate data on the longevity of floppy disks is troublesome to source but estimates on the lifespan on magnetic tape (in the same broad family of storage media as floppy discs) range from between 1 and 30 years (Van Bogart, 1995). The risk of both bitstream and physical disc degradation increases over time.

The aim of the Flashback project was to gain a more comprehensive understanding of these issues and gather empirical data to inform decision-making regarding preservation actions for legacy born digital acquisitions. Initially scoped as a single Proof of Concept project to run over six months, it had three main objectives:

1. To devise a bit-level preservation process for legacy handheld content stored on disks
2. To test migration and emulation workflows designed to deliver authentic representations of content into the reading rooms
3. To make recommendations on turning the Proof of Concept workflows into Business as Usual processes.

For the Proof of Concept, the scope of the project was mostly limited to disk-based collections that were acquired as part of hybrid acquisitions, i.e. acquired as an insert or attachment to a physical item such as book or a magazine. This included CDs and DVDs, as well as 3.5” and 5.25” floppy disks. Older media (e.g. cassette tapes) and newer storage types (e.g. USB sticks) were deemed to be out of scope for the project due to the short time frame available. Audio content was also not considered, as this is being addressed by a major British Library programme known as *Save our Sounds*. Three work packages define the work carried out in the project: collection profiling, content extraction, and content preservation.

Collection Profiling & Content Sampling

Collection profiling is an established process used by the British Library to develop overviews of specific types of collection (e.g., e-journals, web archives, geospatial data) and to define the Library’s preservation intent for the material in that collection (Day et al., 2014). Legacy born-digital material from hybrid acquisitions had not previously been included in this process, so the first stage of the project was the development of a

¹ The phrase ‘Institutional obsolescence’ is used to identify the context in which the technology used to access the content is obsolete. It is preferred over general use of the term obsolescence, which lacks scope and consideration of operational and financial limitations

collection profile, in order to inform the selection of a suitable sample of content for our experiments and to initiate discussions with curators about preservation intent. It introduced digital preservation staff to those responsible for managing the storage facilities in which these materials were kept and ultimately led to the production of a 200-item 'long list,' from which a subsequent registry of 91 and final shortlist of 50 items were selected.

The sampling approach used was a relatively crude attempt to apply some logic to the selection process. The long list was developed through physical analysis of the material located upon a percentage of the shelves. When developing this list, staff made notes of the different types of material discovered, and the different technical rendering environments they relied upon. In order to make some distinctions between the types of content on each disc, items were also classified in terms of their content type. Analysis of the long list identified the following variations:

- Data (Film)
- Data (Film/Sound)
- Data (Film/Images)
- Data (Spreadsheets)
- Data (Text)
- Games
- Guides
- Software (Application)
- Software (Educational)
- Software (O/S)
- Software (Programming)
- Software (Simulation)
- Software (Utilities)

The long list was then sampled to produce a smaller registry, and the resulting items analysed to identify items with unique or near-unique combinations of technical and content criteria. This produced a final shortlist of 50 items, attempting to ensure that the Proof of Concept was able to test a broad range of different combinations, as represented in the collection as a whole. It is acknowledged that this selection process did not necessarily result in a fully representative sample, particularly with regards to the proportional distribution of items across different generations of technology and content types, but the resulting sample did nonetheless sufficiently represent the range of different types of material to be found. Items in the sample dated from 1980 to 2010. Original environments represented by the shortlist included the BBC Micro, MS-DOS, Apple ® II, Mac 7, Mac 9, and several variations of Microsoft Windows ® (3.x, 95 and 2000).

Content Extraction

Content extraction (hereafter referred to as disk imaging) proved more time consuming than expected. It was not always immediately clear whether the problem lay with the disk, the legacy hardware being used (especially for 5.25" disks), or the software extraction program. Workflows for content extraction were tested, refined, and documented in an internal wiki, with issues documented in a corresponding Observations Log.

A generic workflow was developed that progressed through twelve stages:

1. Check disk and insert into drive
2. Calculate MD5 checksums for files on physical media (optical disc / floppy disk). Save to text file
3. Create image file from physical media using extraction command
4. Mount image as a read-only file system
5. Virus check image
6. Calculate MD5 checksum for mounted image file. Compare to checksum for original disk and highlight any discrepancies
7. Unmount image file
8. Unmount physical media, remove from device
9. Copy image file to external hard drive
10. Attach external hard drive to networked machine and perform second virus scan
11. Upload image file to NAS server
12. Create a METS record containing PREMIS event information about the creation of the disk image, required operational environment (e.g. OS, etc.)

This generic workflow provided the foundation for development of more granular versions for specific storage media. In terms of imaging tools, the project tested BitCurator, ISO Buster and Kryoflux, settling on Bitcurator as the preferred tool for imaging CDs, DVDs and 3.5" floppy discs. Kryoflux was used to image the 5.25" floppy discs. The particular steps for working with these tools and storage media were included in the granular workflows.

Although the imaging process overall took longer than expected, the outcome was in most cases positive. Seventeen items stored on CD-ROM were included in the sample, comprising twenty-two discs altogether, as some items were comprised of multiple discs. Only one of the twenty-two CDs failed imaging due to the disc being physically damaged. The standard extraction script was successful for all but one of the remaining items (published in 1992). This disc could not be detected in either of the optical drives on the BitCurator system and had instead to be viewed on a Windows system. ISO Buster was used to create a standard image file, which was mountable on both Windows and Linux systems.

All four DVD-ROM items were imaged successfully. The standard extraction script was successful in all cases.

Ten items stored on 3.5" floppy disks were included in the sample, comprising twenty-nine disks altogether. Two of the 3.5" floppy disks failed imaging, in both cases due to physical damage to the disk. The standard extraction script was successful in all but one of the remaining items. The Macintosh version of that particular item was not readable using the standard script due to its non-standard disk geometry. The KryoFlux extraction script was instead used, with the KryoFlux board connected to the 3.5" floppy disk drive instead of the 5.25" floppy drive. Extraction was successful using this script.

Nineteen items stored on 5.25" floppy disks were included in the sample, comprising twenty-three disks. Three disks failed extraction (all items based on a single floppy disc), as listed below:

1. The raw stream data could only be partially interpreted by the KryoFlux software. Using the "Apple II" disk profile - which was successful with other items - allowed track 1 to be read successfully, but no other tracks, resulting in an unmountable disk image of only 9KB. All allowable variations of this disk profile were attempted without any further success
2. No disk could be detected by the KryoFlux software; the message "the streaming device reported missing index - no disk in drive" was reported. The KryoFlux support forums indicated that this error is usually caused by a faulty or incompatible floppy disk drive.
3. The image was apparently created successfully, but problems were encountered when loaded into the BBC emulator (BeebEm). The contents of the mounted image could be viewed, but running the bootloader simply caused the emulator to sit at a blank screen indefinitely. For the time being this is being recorded as a faulty disc image but further investigation is needed to confirm this.

These results provided the following data:

Percentage of CDs to fail the imaging process	4.5%
Percentage of DVDs to fail the imaging process	0
Percentage of 3.5" floppy disks to fail the imaging process	3.5%
Percentage of 5.25" floppy disks to fail the imaging process	13%
Average time taken to image a CD	5 minutes 50 seconds
Average time taken to image a DVD	16 minutes 34 seconds
Average time taken to image a 3.5" floppy disk	1 minute 10 seconds
Average time taken to image a 5.25" floppy disk	2 minutes 26 seconds

As we have previously acknowledged, the sample from which these results have been derived is small. Larger scale testing is vital to ensure accuracy. Discs that could not be imaged have been excluded from the average times.

Content Preservation

A fundamental objective of the project was the testing of emulation and migration processes designed to deliver authentic representations of the content to reading room computers. A laboratory was established and populated with the legacy computing equipment required to provide ‘native’ access to material contained in the sample. After testing and learning how to use the machines, project members were then able to run and assess the materials in their native environment before comparing them with the ‘preserved’ versions delivered on modern PCs.

Equipment for the Lab was sourced mainly from staff or eBay and over a period of four months the Lab was populated with the following items:

- Macintosh Classic
- Power Macintosh G3 (Blue & White G3)
- British Broadcasting Master Series Microcomputer (BBC Master)
- Compaq Portable 386
- Amstrad PPC 512
- Amstrad PC1640DD
- Amstrad PC 1512 SD
- RM Nimbus
- Siemens NIXDORF
- Apple IIe
- Compaq Deskpro
- HP Omnibook 6000
- AcerNote Light 350PC
- Apple Mac Pro 2.26 (A1289)

Purchase of legacy equipment was relatively inexpensive and came in significantly under budget at £400. Use of the equipment was not always straightforward and an excellent example of why reliance on old hardware is not a suitable preservation approach. Some items were temperamental and one in particular seemed to display a different error message every other time it was switched on. We also found out that research was often required for younger staff to work out how to use some of the older equipment. As might be expected with hybrid content, an understanding of the content itself often required consultation with the printed counterpart to the item.

Three main preservation approaches were examined:

- The Emulation-as-a-Service (EaaS) offering from the University of Freiburg (von Suchodoletz, 2013; Liebetaut, 2014;)
- The Interject Solution developed by the British Library as part of the SCAPE project (Jackson, 2014)
- Migration workflows, details of which varied depending on the source and target formats.

A decision tree was produced that differentiated between content types in order to inform selection of an initial approach for testing in the Lab. The tree excludes Interject

as a short review revealed it to be unsuitable for the Proof of Concept due to its prototype status with limited support for different environments.

Figure 1. The Flashback Preservation Planning Decision Tree.

The decision tree evolved slightly during the initial process of running the disks in the Lab, after we had begun to identify the importance of the disks' directory structures. This resulted in the identification of two main emulation paths: a) for objects where the folder structure was integral to navigation of the content, and b) for objects where software applications were intended to be run directly. The decision tree proved mostly accurate on the question of appropriate preservation approaches for different types of content, though we again acknowledge the limitations of a small sample and the need for further testing. Use of the tree during the course of the project also led to the following observations:

1. *It is important to base preservation planning decisions on the observed behaviour of content objects:* Initial decisions about preservation planning were often based on the (relatively limited) information available in the registry. However, our knowledge of the sample content objects developed as we gained more experience with using the content in an approximation of its original environment as well as with our other tools (especially the Emulation-as-a-Service environment).
2. *It is important to take into account the granularity of content:* As expected, most disks (especially the CDs and DVDs) contained more than one content type, including software.

3. *An additional category is needed covering source code and other items where emulation or migration would not an appropriate approach at present:* Several items in the sample primarily contained source code; others contained complete operating systems or required particular hardware, and these were added to the list of items that would not be migrated or emulated by the project. We still need to explore in more detail what preservation might mean for these objects.
4. *Implicit knowledge contained within disk directory structures:* For example, one CD contained research datasets in CSV format where the original files would have, on the face of it, been a prime candidate for a migration approach. However, the way the files were arranged on the disk did provide some additional context, e.g. the results from particular experiments/instruments were stored in separate folders, datasets were supported by plain-text "readme" files, etc. It was clear that the directory arrangement would be of use to anyone within the "designated communities" of those particular datasets. Any chosen migration approach (e.g. file extraction and packaging) would need to retain some aspects of the original directory structure. Simple emulation of the disk, however, might provide a more straightforward way of doing the same thing, whereby the disk content could be investigated, then selected datasets of interest could be extracted (i.e. removed from the emulation environment) for further analysis.

A simple process was developed to analyse, document, and compare rendering of item significant characteristics in both 'native' and 'preserved' form. Using the five attributes identified by Rothenberg (Rothenberg & Bikson, 1999; Rothenberg 2000), the project team ran an initial analysis of each item and documented these on an experiment plan, then ran the experiment using the approach indicated by the decision tree. Some items underwent multiple experiments, depending on the viability of the first approach tested.

The EaaS platform installed for the Library by the University of Freiburg was a demo installation, hosted on an Ubuntu 14.04 VM and providing MS-DOS, Windows 3.1, Mac OS 7.5 and 9.0 emulators. Staff also installed three stand-alone emulators of Apple II, BBC Micro and MS-DOS/PC-DOS environments.

Emulation results overview

In line with the decision tree, emulation approaches were tested on several items from the sample with interactive elements. Results are presented in the table below.

Environment	Emulation tool	#Items	Results
Apple II	Apple Win (local)	2	Very successful in replicating original behaviour. Quicker keyboard reaction with preserved version than on original hardware.
BBC Micro	BeebEm (local)	1	Very successful in replicating both appearance and behaviour of software. Emulator also mimics the audio experience of a BBC Micro by replicating the sound of

			a disk running
MS-DOS	DOSBox (local)	6	Success with two items; unsatisfactory delivery of one when content could not be viewed beyond the main menu. Three items could not be compared with the original environment due to unresolved BASICA software dependency.
MS-DOS	QEMU (EaaS)	3	Success with two items; unsatisfactory delivery of one when content could not be viewed beyond the main menu.
Mac 7.0	BasiliskII (EaaS)	6	Results varied; three experiments judged as satisfactory, two as unsatisfactory and one with a dependency which made us unable to run it. Both unsatisfactory experiments had issues with audio
Mac 9.0	Sheepshaver (EaaS)	2	Both items judged as satisfactory. Note that unlike the failed items in BasiliskII this sample does not contain any sound features
Windows 3.1	Qemu (EaaS)	8	Success with four items; issues with four items relating to video rendering, graphical glitches/distorted images or audio issues.
Windows 95/98	Qemu (EaaS)	7	Success with four items; issues with three items relating to video rendering and graphics.

Migration results overview

In line with the decision tree, a small number of migration approaches were tested on text documents and spreadsheets. In the main, these experiments were based on attempting to open files using later versions of appropriate software, i.e. using the format conversion facility of this software to undertake the appropriate transformations. These migration items required a smaller range of original environments than those requiring emulation, namely MS-DOS and Windows (versions of). It was not possible to acquire original software for the MS-DOS experiments so our assessments in that environment are incomplete. We noted however that one item could not be opened successfully by any of the migration tools tested (Open Office, LibreOffice and MS Excel) though it could be rendered using Qemu emulation software. The same issue occurred with a different item from a Windows 3.1 environment. Items from a native Windows 95 environment contained CSV files that rendered well with MS Microsoft Excel 2010.

The project team also ran three migration approaches with interactive items as they required relatively recent hardware and software (Windows XP and 2000). Running these on Windows 7, only one item was problematic. This was due to DRM issues, caused by attempting to run the program from a disk-image rather than the original disc.

Conclusions & Next Steps

Emulation consistently and perhaps unsurprisingly yielded better results than migration in terms of behaviour and appearance. The small sample used in this project suggests that the older material (such as Apple II and BBC Micro) emulates successfully as long as dependent software is available.² For multi-environment disks, e.g. those designed to run in both a Windows and Mac environment, the Mac environments performed better than the Windows ones. Emulation results for each generation were identical between locally installed emulators and EaaS. Memory in the Freiburg system was an issue with later generations of software and this was easier to address with local emulators. However, setting up EaaS emulators was slightly quicker than local installations, especially with multi disk installations which generally run smoothly in EaaS following recent upgrades.

The limitations of working with such a small sample have been referenced several times in this paper and these are recognised by both the project team and project board. As a result, a second phase of Flashback is currently being scoped that will use a much larger sample and consider objectives which were not able to be fully addressed in phase one, such as the deployment of solutions at scale and in an on-demand situation for readers. Further work is also required to answer questions around the user experience, the costs of deployment at scale, and the role of a software repository in the preservation of legacy material. This work should be complete by the end of 2016.

The age of the material being tested in this project has allowed us to move beyond preservation theory and to begin to analyse the realities of undertaking digital preservation in practice. The value of this project lies not just in its use to the Library itself, but also in sharing our experiences and delivering evidence to the wider community of the comparative benefits and practicalities of using migration and emulation approaches *in situ*.

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² Software dependencies are especially challenging for some of the older material (MS-DOS). Newer software has, unlike the MS-DOS generation, often contained a copy of additional software required to run the disc.

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